

Educational Funding as A Correlate of Students' Academic Achievement in Kwara State Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The current situation of secondary education in Kwara State suggests that things may get worse unless measures are taken to address the problem of underfunding. If this problem is not addressed, the outcome may negatively influence students' academic achievement. This study therefore investigated educational funding as a correlate of students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population for this study consisted of 18,109 teachers and students whose results were used in all public secondary schools in Kwara State. The sample for the study consisted of 600 teachers and students whose results were used in 60 public secondary schools in Kwara State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. An instrument tagged Educational Funding Questionnaire (EFQ) was used to collect relevant data for the study. The second instrument was an Inventory on Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination results. The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by Educational Management and Test and Measurements experts. The reliability of EFQ was determined through the test re-test method and correlation coefficient value of 0.85 was obtained for EFQ. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that Government funding, parent funding and institutional funding were significantly related to students' academic achievement. It was recommended among others that parents should supplement government funding of secondary education through PTA and provision of needed facilities which could lead to better students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Educational Funding, Students, Academic Achievement,

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Introduction

Studies have revealed that there has been a downward trend in educational achievement of students in Nigerian Secondary Schools in general and in Kwara State in particular. The 2017 – 2019 Senior School Certificate Examination result released by West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) attested to this claim that there is descending trend in the achievement of students in Kwara State that was not graded among the first twenty based on students' achievement. Parents, teachers, Curriculum experts have also uttered considerable worry about this low achievement in external examination such as West African Examination Council. It is assumed in some instances that the academic achievement of students is facing a lot of abandonment and problems due to lack of funds. The educational system in Nigeria appears to be confronted with so many monetary challenges which have eventually brought about a fast decline in the quality of education.

The researcher observed that the insufficient funding of education seems to be the reason for the poor achievement of the students in Secondary Schools in Kwara State. Secondary Schools in Kwara State are apparently not well funded as this could be seen through terrible learning conditions of the students, poor learning situation, challenge of textbooks, problem of teaching aid, low provision for training of teachers and inadequate facilities to improve comprehension and skills.

Funding Secondary education in Kwara State has become a matter of public concern as a result of the present financial down turn and worldwide inflation. According to Central Bank of Nigeria (2019), poor funding has been the misery of Nigerian educational system to the level that the budgetary allocation has been very low. In several Secondary Schools in Kwara State, the researcher observed that as many as four classes are put up in one classroom and these are classes that are already congested and in deplorable state. In addition, laboratories and apparatuses appear to be grossly insufficient and the attendant challenges seem to affect learners' academic achievement.

Considering the necessity of sources of educational funding and its effect on students' academic achievement in Schools, this study's intent was to investigate specifically selected variables such as funds from institution, parents and government.

The government of Nigeria recognized the vital role of education on the life and growth of human resources, and hence the relevance of adequate monetary commitment from all the three tiers of government for effective execution of educational programmes in Nigeria. In Nigeria, Secondary education derives its major fund from the annual allocation to the education sector by the government.

Unfortunately, it seems the apportionment to the education sector on which Secondary education depends has been constantly low in spite of the vital role of the sector in the training of manpower for the development of the economy. Statistics (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2019) showed that between 2000 and 2018, allocation to the education sector by Federal Government in Nigeria was not more than 14% of the annual budget. Furthermore, out of the three levels of education in Nigeria, tertiary education receives the largest portion of Education Vote, thus showing that the remaining fund is to be shared by Primary and Secondary education (Hinchliffe, 2002). It has even been the practice of States to make provision for Secondary education from the distribution to the education sector, which in most cases has been in form of consecutive grant to schools, on term or session basis and depending on the size of enrolment of each school.

The Researcher observed that the UNESCO recommendation of 26% of the annual budget to education is never followed in Nigeria talk less in Kwara State. Secondary education

in Kwara state seems to be grossly underfunded and this shows in poor quality of education, low provision of human and material resources in Schools.

The government in a bid to find another means of funding of education decided to partly delegate funding of Secondary education to parents not minding their income levels and other economic burden. The duty of nurturing a child is dependent on the parents. These tallies with the common assertions by sociologist, that education can be an instrument of socialisation which is being taught from home. It is relevant to imagine that parental financial involvement in education can have possible consequences on the academic achievement of children in school.

Parents have for long been known for their vital role in funding schools right from the colonial era especially after the First World War had disturbed funds from missionaries to run schools (Sekamwa, 2007). Parents' income level is seen as a major basis of their level of involvement in the funding of education. Parents' input in funding not only targets school fees but may also involve students' personal requirements that allow them acquire education easily. Caro (2009) discovered the relationship between parental funding of education and academic achievement as pleasant. The researcher also observed that children of parents who do not sponsor the education of their children seem to be behind children who are adequately sponsored by their parents. This may be reason why students of private schools appear to perform better than students of public schools.

Currently, Secondary education in Kwara state is majorly funded by the state government. The researcher observed that the State allocation to Secondary Schools in Kwara state is always very lean, as this does not boost successful achievement of Secondary education goals in Kwara state. So there is need for schools to generate money so as to fund some School activities though there is a fixed cost that must be paid by the government if we must achieve common access to education. Various institutional financing of secondary education as observed by the researcher include PTA, proceeds from the community involvement, rebate from school vendors, school farm, endowments, fund raising activities, donations, old students associations among others.

This study therefore investigated educational funding as a correlate of students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. The study specifically examined:

- i. the relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement;
- ii. the relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement;
- iii. the relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement; and
- iv. the contribution of the sources of educational funding to students' academic achievement.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.
2. There is no significant relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.
3. There is no significant relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.
4. Sources of educational funding will not significantly contribute to students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population for this study consisted of 18,109 teachers and students whose results were used in all public secondary schools in Kwara State. The sample for the study consisted of 600 teachers to assess the sources of educational funding and students whose results were used in 60 public secondary schools in Kwara State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

An instrument tagged Educational Funding Questionnaire (EFQ) was used to collect relevant data for the study. The second instrument was an Inventory on Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination results. *Section A* of the EFQ sought for background information about the respondents while *Section B* consisted of 30 items. Likert type 4 point rating scale of preference was used as follows: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The inventory was used to collect data on students' grades in subjects written at the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination level in the May/June of 2016/2017, 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 sessions. The same scale was adopted to classify the results of the students as 5 credits and above including Mathematics and English, 5 credits and above including either Mathematics or English, 5 credits and above without English and Mathematics and Less than 5 credits.

The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by Educational Management and Test and Measurements experts. The instruments were said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, the instrument claim to measure. The reliability of the Educational Funding Questionnaire (EFQ) was determined through the test re-test method carried out in 2 secondary schools outside the sampled area. A correlation coefficient value of 0.85 was obtained for EFQ which was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean standard deviation and graphs, while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.

Table 1: Relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	p-value
Government Funding	60	23.71	1.74	0.371*	0.014
Students' Academic Achievement	60	3.06	0.19		

*P<0.05

Table 1 showed r-cal (0.371) is significant because the p-value (0.014) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. Hence, Government funding of education is positively and moderately related to students' academic achievement.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.

Table 2: Relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	p-value
Parental Funding	60	28.44	1.32	0.602*	0.000
Students' Academic Achievement	60	3.06	0.19		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed r-cal (0.602) is significant because the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. Hence, parental funding of education is positively and moderately related to students' academic achievement.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.

Table 3: Relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	p-value
Institutional Funding	60	24.08	1.51	0.417*	0.000
Students' Academic Achievement	60	3.06	0.19		

*P<0.05

Table 3 showed r-cal (0.417) is significant because the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. Hence, institutional funding of education is positively and moderately related to students' academic achievement.

Hypothesis 4: Sources of educational funding will not significantly contribute to students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools.

Table 8: Multiple Regression showing Contribution of sources of educational funding on Students' Academic Achievement

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	T	R	R ²	F
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	2.368	.249		9.510	0.804	0.646	24.011
Government Funding	.018	.005	.362	3.600			
Parents Funding	.038	.008	.589	4.750			
Institutional Funding	.025	.006	.461	4.167			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

Table 4 indicates that the F-cal value of 24.011 is significant at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected. Hence, sources of educational funding would significantly contribute to students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary

schools. All the sub-variables such as government funding, parental funding and institutional funding account for 64.6 percent of students' academic achievement ($R^2 = 0.646$, $p < 0.05$).

The result showed that government funding, parents funding and institutional funding of sub-variables of educational funding positively contributed to students' academic achievement with government funding having a beta weight of ($\beta = 0.362$, $p < 0.05$), parents funding ($\beta = 0.589$, $p < 0.05$) and institutional funding ($\beta = 0.461$, $p < 0.05$). The table also shows that parental funding of education is the highest contributor to students' academic achievement while government funding of education is the least contributor to students' academic achievement.

The resulting regression equation is given as:

$$Y = 2.368 + 0.018X_1 + 0.038X_2 + 0.025X_3$$

where:

Y	=	Students' Academic Achievement
X ₁	=	Government Funding of Education
X ₂	=	Parents Funding of Education
X ₃	=	Institutional Funding of Education

Discussion

The study revealed a significant relationship between Government funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. The probable reason for this finding could be because of the important role the government plays in funding of secondary education. The research conducted by Gupta and Verhoeven (2001) reveals that the scale and efficiency of government education investment plays a very important role in the process of promoting students' academic achievement. This result is consistent with previous findings of other scholars such as Gupta and Verhoeven (2011) and Jefferson (2005) who all found a positive relationship between government funding of education and students' academic achievement. However, Picus and Robillard (2010) found out that government funding of education has no significant influence on students' achievement. The result indicated that students from schools well-funded by the government will perform well in school. It could be inferred that students' academic achievement will be above average if public schools are well funded by the government.

It was further revealed that there was significant relationship between parental funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. The researcher is of the view that when parents support the financing of education through the support they give their children, students are likely to be motivated to perform academically well. Parents' participation in financing not only focuses on school fees but may also include students' personal requirements that enable them acquire education easily. These may include clothing, note books and proper medication when they fall sick both at home and at school. This finding supports the contention of Sirin (2015), Caro (2009) and Udida, Ukway and Ogodo (2012) who concluded that a significant relationship existed between parent financing of education and students' academic achievement. The implication of this finding is that if parents supplement government financing of secondary education, it will lead to better students' academic achievement.

The study also revealed a significant relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement in Kwara State secondary schools. The probable reason this finding might be because of the fact that the state government cannot adequately fund the secondary education alone. This result is consistent with previous findings of other scholars such as Caro (2009) and Nwakpa (2007) who all found a positive

relationship between institutional funding of education and students' academic achievement. It could be inferred that for secondary school to be well funded, the institution must internally generate fund to support other sources of educational funding.

The study also revealed that sources of educational funding significantly contributed to the students' academic achievement. The three sources acting as predictors had effect on students' academic achievement at varying degrees. Parental funding of education has the highest predictive strength while government funding of education has the least predictive strength on students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that Government funding, parent funding and institutional funding of education would go a long way to improve students' academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The government should release running grants to schools before the academic session begins.
2. Parents should supplement government funding of secondary education through PTA and provision of needed facilities which could lead to better students' academic achievement.
3. Secondary school administrators should work out means to internally generate funds to augment other sources of educational funding for smooth running of the school.

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